

The Impact Of Viral Marketing On Competitive Intelligence A Study Of A Sample Of Managers At The Iraqi Fashion House Institute Of Administration, Middle Technical University, Iraq

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Abstract

The research aimed to identify the impact and relationship of viral marketing on competitive intelligence. The sample consisted of (30) managers at the Iraqi Fashion House. (51) Paragraphs were used to be distributed on a set of dimensions. Using the statistical program (SPSS), the researcher reached the following results: The response rate for the alternative (strongly agreed upon) was (65%), which is the highest percentage among the alternatives to the answer, as the results indicated that the value of the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (0.960), and the researcher graduated with a set of conclusions and proposals.

Introduction

The starting point of this study refers to the reality of the rapid shifts towards the economics of knowledge as the role of intangible resources in achieving sustainable competitive advantage grows, and the Internet has become the main strategic information tool to reach competitiveness in the business environment of various organizations, and this network will become the next main field towards the growth and development of the function of competitive intelligence in contemporary organizations and is a good source of information about the competitive environment including the history of the organization and overviews of it, in terms of products and services provided. Financial statements, sales figures, annual reports, press releases, and the biography of senior executives and these statements are valuable in providing us with direct and indirect contextual information to enable the competitive intelligence professional to analyze the organization's strategies, and the reasons for attracting experts and users of competitive intelligence to use the Internet is that most of the information available is free in addition to the presence of some utility tools such as search engines that shorten a lot of time and effort, when searching for relevant information on the Internet and then analyzing information Combined in the right context, and the importance of the relationship and impact between viral marketing and competitive intelligence, which depends directly on the information provided by the Internet and the employment of this relationship to achieve the objectives of the organization, this research was prepared to highlight three investigations devoted the first to the methodology of research and the second to the theoretical framework while allocating the third research to the practical aspect of it.

The first topic/ systematicframework

The study adopted the descriptive analytical approach in the study of the variable of research (viral marketing and competitive intelligence), and in the following framework:

First: the problem of the study

Alternative resources for information required to build competitive intelligence are not available and insufficient, for fear of obtaining information already available to the organization without the use of intelligence effort, and the information required is unlikely to become available to the organization through other traditional means unless the organized intelligence effort is used.

Viral marketing is a strategic source of management of the organization that seeks to build real competitive intelligence, and because the relationship and impact between these two variables are still unclear, the research problem has been identified through the following questions:

1. What is the conceptual framework for research change changers (viral marketing competitive intelligence)?
2. Is there a relationship and effect of viral marketing to competitive intelligence?

Second: The hypothesis of the study

Is there a moral connection and effect of viral marketing in competitive intelligence?

Third: The objectives of the study

1. To define the concept and importance of viral marketing and its role in organizations.
2. Highlight the process of competitive intelligence and how its tools are influenced by viral marketing activities.
3. Learn about the nature of the relationship and the impact between viral marketing and competitive intelligence.
4. Make practical recommendations to business organizations to keep up with rapid developments in viral marketing and competitive intelligence.

Fourth: The importance of the study

This study is particularly important as one of the attempts to highlight the concept of viral marketing and competitive intelligence and link them, which contributes to enriching the Arab Library and modern marketing research in Iraqi universities with a study in this field, and shows the applied importance of this study in the desired results, which may contribute to a strategic understanding of viral marketing because it is of great importance in increasing the

profits of organizations and reducing their promotional costs, which may help to develop more marketing strategies, through the window of competitive intelligence in this field and its role.

Fifth: Data collection and analysis

A questionnaire was adopted that included two parts, the first of which was devoted to viral marketing and included (21) questions from (1-21), while the second part was devoted to competitive intelligence by (22) questions of (22-43), and the statistical program(Spss) was used in the analysis of data.

6thA: Previous studies

Table 1 shows several studies conducted in the field of research variables

Title of the study	(journal m/c reviews cyclopedia)
Researcher and Year	Study (Hospers, 2002)
The objective of the study	Launch a viral campaign by posting tv ads on the Internet
From the results of the study	- Sales increased by 12% compared to 2001/00, and the number of people who watched these films was more than eleven million viewers.
Title of the study	(Multi-stage online viral marketing model)
Researcher and Year	Study (Debrmyn, linen, 2003)
The objective of the study	Thee-knowledge aims to know the role of the spoken word through the Internet in the decision-making stages
From the results of the study	- There is a moral relationship between the sender and the recipient, and the opening of the personal website.

Title of the study	Food Company Study
Researcher and Year	kettle, 2005
The objective of the study	plement the company strategy to develop new chips with different flavors than the flavors it produced
From the results of the study	Increasing the size of the market and creating a class at the level of a larger market.
Title of the study	(Dave, goffer, 2006)
Researcher and Year	Dave, goffer, 2006
The objective of the study	Learn about individual trends about different forms of viral marketing
From the results of the study	73% are aware of emails. 38% of customers have positive trends and would like to send back the

	message they received.
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Seventh: Study model: -

The search model reflects the relationship and impact between the viral marketing variables and competitive intelligence, and accordingly

The analysis required to come up with the required conclusions and recommendations as follows: -

Viral marketing dimensions

0 - Associated strategies. Communities.

The most important ^{viral} marketing strategies should be mentioned.

1- Low integration strategy. High integration strategy.

We will briefly explain the meaning of these two types of viral marketing strategies: -

1. Low Integration Strategy: - It relies on the republication of the message received by the customer from his site by clicking on the message sent and gets rewarded from the website sent to the message and uses this strategy to spread a wide variety of products that are dealt with by electronic marketing organizations, and Hotmail has achieved great success through the use of this strategy.
2. High integration strategy: - It relies on informing its users of the presence of their colleagues registered on the mailing lists as increasing the number of users encouraged by the user to use the website will result in more benefits and will motivate them to spread the message, Amazon has achieved. Com) is a great success in motivating and directing its users to gain new customers for the home page of the company's website.

The dimensions of viral marketing can include:

- 1- Viral marketing campaigns: Ads that have similarity or symmetry in terms of the message you carry, and that appear or prove in an ad medium over a specified period.
- 2- Electronic means of publishing: virtual electronic communities over the Internet allow subscribers of all ages, races, and countries to create their accounts, through which the subscriber exchanges messages, photos, and videos, or communicates via email or chat rooms.
- 3- Physical stimulation: Organizations that adopt viral marketing plant the first seeds of the idea through the free means addresses or offerings by certain people selected by their marketers while developing the incentive to post them virally to all those who communicate with them.
- 4- Influential opinion leaders: Recent studies have shown that many public and influential figures through social media sites greatly influence the lives of their followers, which makes their marketing of products and brands through their accounts very effective.
- 5- Purchase Decision: Many of the communication sites, provide unbiased information because they rely on third parties providing advice and advice where the buyer can interact with other customers who have purchased the goods or services provided by the website and access the complaints by customers who have a bad experience with the product.

Second: Competitive intelligence

Competitive intelligence is a process of planning to obtain information within ethical and legal frameworks related to the internal and external environment, analysis, and processing to help make decisions that will ensure the achievement of the organization's competitive ^{advantage}

Several definitions have been defined, including what ^{he} said as a "systematic and ethical program for collecting, analyzing and managing information that can affect the organization's plans, decisions, and processes."

He ^{identified} it is a "regular program for collecting and analyzing information on competitors' activities and business trends to achieve and develop the organization's objectives."

It is also known as "the ability to extract highly confidential vital information about competitors using some confidential and non-confidential information, to formulate an appropriate competitive strategy for study and modification whenever necessary and before it is too ^{late}."

Therefore, it does not depart from what the Competitive Intelligence Professional Association has said, which considers competitive intelligence to be a process of ethical collection, analysis, and dissemination of accurate, specific, and relevant intelligence information, appropriate timing, insight, and sufficient about the applications of the business environment, competitors and organization itself.

Competitive intelligence is a tactical analysis of markets, competitors, and industries to allow short- and long-term decision-making to take advantage of the changes in the market and exploit the strengths and weaknesses of competitors and make them for the benefit of the organization.

The importance of competitive intelligence in the y-bis followed by:

- 1- E-competitive intelligence is an effective process for the organization, by supporting the decision-making process at all levels and for a variety of research and development.
- 2- Competitive intelligence can allocate resources to organizations according to their size, especially those in technology industries.
- 3- Structured competitive intelligence helps at the stage of the production process by understanding the pricing structures of competitors and understanding the manufacturing process and its impact on production costs that enables and, especially when launching a new product.
- 4- Competitive intelligence continuously monitors the aso-s, which is characterized by short and continuous changes. The effective role and added value-added by competitive intelligence to the development of organizations are the following points:
 - 1- Plan for and maintain a high market share.
 - 2- Anticipate the reactions of competitors, and work to counter them.
 - 3- Competitive intelligence is a strategic management device and one of the business areas that provide rapid growth and improvement in organizations

The life cycle of competitive intelligence goes through a series of stages that will be addressed with some briefness as follows.

- 1- Planning and guidance: Organizations vary in their construction of the competitive intelligence process, as the building blocks of this building depend on the focus these organizations place on the competitive intelligence process in particular, as well as on the industry in which the organization operates and the competitive intelligence process is not just the process of collecting a lot of data and information that managers believe they need, but on issues of great importance to executive management.
- 2- Assembly phase: At this stage, the focus should be on the sucking and using of information and focusing on legal principles when collecting information as part of the competitive intelligence process and perhaps one of the difficult tasks facing competitive intelligence in organizations is to gather information associated with early warning of the movements of impending competitors.
- 3- Analysis phase: An important key step that includes analyzing the data collected to determine the factors and relationships of the current activity, which will improve planning and sound decision-making.
- 4- The deployment phase is the process of transferring the results obtained from competitive intelligence to the parties with the authority and responsibility to act based on these results.
- 5- Structure (process): Competitive intelligence requires appropriate policies and procedures and formal or informal infrastructure so that individuals working in the organization can actively contribute to the process of generating competitive intelligence.
- 6- Culture and awareness organizers: For the organization to benefit from the efforts of competitive intelligence correctly, and to become a successful practice, the organization must support this culture within its organization so that knowledge and ideas can be established and shared between individuals and departments within the organization.

There are also a range of conditional variables that affect the effectiveness of generating competitive intelligence in business organizations, including these variables:

- 1- Competitive Intelligence Network: A range of relatively stable and informal personal information sources, fed by a competitive intelligence analyzer, there is a range of dimensions that affect the efficiency of generating the competitive intelligence process within the network and include:
 - Network coverage: Extensiveness of a network refers to the number of people in the informal competitive intelligence network, as the number of people increases the number of people in the network will increase significantly.
 - Third-party technique: Third-party technique by requesting some information about a competitor from another party linked to the competitor that we want to get information about, due to the difficulty of obtaining that information directly.
 - Analog: Homophile: The lower the analog in the competitive intelligence network, the greater the level of comprehensiveness and accuracy of the information that can be obtained from the search process, and there will be greater confidence in the competitive intelligence information generated.

- KnowledgeSupply: Issue knowledge is important in the process of generating competitive intelligence is the extent to which the individuals working in the organization are aware of the importance of the information they have about competitors and the provision of competitive intelligence analysts.
 - Maintaining exchange: Reciprocity maintenance as much as we maintain the exchange of information between individuals working within the organization's internal network, will increase the comprehensiveness, accuracy, and timing of information, and will reduce the competitive intelligence analyst's reliance on non-personal sources.
 - Promotion effort: Promotion effort contributes to the promotion of competitive intelligence activity in a range of benefits, namely, increasing the knowledge supply process by individual employees, and maintaining the exchange of information within the organization's internal network.
- 2- Business environment: The aspects of the internal and external environment of the organization, in terms of the characteristics of these environments and how they affect the processes of the organization, research, and awareness-making sense-making, there is a range of dimensions the effectiveness of the process of generating competitive intelligence in the business environment include:
- Awareness systems: Recognition systems refer to official and informal rewards to gain participation with competitive intelligence as these systems facilitate the flow of information horizontally and vertically within the organization.
 - Time allocation: Time allocation in the absence of sufficient time can reduce the number of sources of access to information and its diversity and we can reduce the accuracy of the analysis process, and it is possible to consider the lack of time in the upbringing and analysis of competitive data an important reason for the failure of many competitive intelligence programs.
 - Market pressure: Represents the demands of the organization by key external stakeholders such as competitors, consumers, and shareholders.
- 3- Information Environment: Refers to the information characteristics faced by a competitive IQ analyzer, and includes a range of dimensions that affect the effectiveness of the competitive intelligence generation process, including:
- Richness expresses the amount of information associated with competitors, available in a competitive environment.
 - Conflict of information: Divergence affects the speed of the awareness-making process because of the time it takes to determine which of that information is reliable and valid.
 - Value information: Information value and affect in terms of the comprehensiveness, timing, and accuracy of the information for competitive intelligence.
 - Information Analyst Characteristics: The characteristics of the individuals responsible for generating competitive intelligence and the strategies they use to generate it affect the efficiency of the competitive intelligence generation process.
- Competitive intelligence tools that can be used to obtain intelligence information ^{include:*}
- 1- Website: The organization's website can obtain customer data in a timely and real ^{manner.†}
 - 2- Electronic survey: An attractive tool for many reasons such as easy management by individuals on the internet, and can be discovered through the Internet by the internet and to meet a.
 - 3- Workers in the industry.
 - 4- Databases.
 - 5- Help tools for searching on the internet.
 - 6- Review publications material.

Third Topic / Practical Aspect

First: Research methodology

The researcher relied on the descriptive correlation method because of its suitability for the nature of the research variables as the current research requires knowledge of the correlation between viral marketing and competitive intelligence in the sample.

Second: The Research Community

The research community is made up of the 42 directors of the Iraqi Fashion House in Baghdad, 11 of the directors, 12 assistants, and (19) of the heads of the people, and table (1) shows this.

Table (1) Distribution of the search community by the job, gender, and percentage

T	The government's position	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
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1. Choo, woc teo, T (2009), Assessing the impact of using, the interpret for competitive intelligence, tenor million management Journal, No (39).

(†)Relationship, Bashir (2005) Digital Management Fields and Applications, Emirates Center for Strategic Studies and Research, I1, Abu Dhabi the United Arab Emirates

1	Managers	7	4	11	26,1%
2	Associate	6	6	12	28,5%
3	Heads of the people	6	13	19	45,2%
Total		19	23	42	100%

Third: Description of the research community

Since the current research is classified within the descriptive research methodology, it is necessary to verify the descriptive procedures of the research community to know the numbers in an illustrative way, and accordingly, the researcher adopted the following charts to describe the research community in light of demographic variables and as follows:

1) Sex "male/female"

2) Age " 21-30 years / 31 - 40 years / 40 and above

3) Scientific qualification "Ph.D., Master, High Diploma, Bachelor, Technical Diploma, Others"

4) Years of service "1-5 years, 6-10 years, 11-15 years, 16-20 years, 21-25 years, over 25 years"

5) Internet usage hours

Fourth: Research sample

The current research sample consisted of (30) males and females randomly selected from the research community by (15) male (15) females and table (2) this explains.

Table (2) **Distribution of search sample by the job, gender, and percentage**

T	Government's position	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
1	Managers	4	4	8	26,6%
2	Associate	4	4	8	26,6%
3	Heads of the people	5	9	14	46,6%
Total		13	17	30	100%

Fifth: Search tool

Al-Ba'ath ad has designed a questionnaire that includes a set of paragraphs in light of the definitions of **viral marketing and competitive intelligence**, as it is known as "a marketing strategy that seeks to develop a self-sustaining message through its circulation among internet users and in a continuous and rapid upward way, enabling to gain new customers for the company and increase clear awareness about its products and brand by relying on the Internet, **Competitive intelligence** is known as "a tactical analysis of markets, competitors and industries to allow short- and long-term decision-making, i.e. taking advantage of changes in the market while exploiting competitors' strengths and weaknesses and making them to the benefit of the organization.

The dimensions of each variable were determined according to the theoretical definition of the variable, as the dimensions of viral marketing consisted of (5) dimensions (viral campaigns, electronic publishing methods, physical stimulation, influential opinion leaders, purchasing decision), while the dimensions of competitive intelligence consisted of (6) dimensions (planning and concentration, information gathering, analysis, communication, structure and processes, culture and regulatory awareness) and thus the resolution of (51) paragraphs distributed on the dimensions of the variables, and was presented to a group of experts arbitrators ().

Search model:

Based on the opinions of several researchers in previous studies that review the independent variable (viral marketing) defined in five dimensions (viral campaigns, electronic publishing methods, physical stimulation, influential opinion leaders, purchasing decision), and its effect on the six-dimensional variable (competitive intelligence) (planning, concentration, information aggregation, analysis, communication, structure and processes, culture and regulatory awareness), as shown in figure (1).

Figure (1) Hypothetical Search Chart/ Source: Researcher's Preparations

- (*) Dr. Iyad Mahmoud Al-Rahim.
- Dr. Uday Zuhair
- Dr. Rana Nasser Sabar
- Dr. Salah Mendi Imam
- Dr. Safa Amorteza Said
- D. Safa- Jawad Abdul Hussein
- Dr. Walid Rahima
- Dr. Haitham Abdul Qadir Janabi

Which is the consistency of the terms of each of the main axes of a tool, and their correlation with each other, and to verify the sincerity of internal consistency, the researcher distributed the measure to a survey sample of (30) individuals, by calculating the correlation coefficients between the degree of each axis and the sum of the scores, as shown in the following table:

Table (3) Internal consistency coefficient for resolution

Axis	Communication Transactions	Probability of significance	Resolution
Viral campaigns	0.889 ^(**)	0.001	Slab 0.01
Electronic publishing	0.807 ^(*)	0.000	D at 0.05
Physical stimulation	0.881 ^(**)	0.000	D at 0.01
Influential opinion leaders	0.798 ^(*)	0.000	D at 0.05
Purchase decision	0.787 ^(*)	0.002	D at 0.05
Planning and focus	0.845 ^(**)	0.003	Slab 0.01
Collecting information	0.862 ^(**)	0.000	D at 0.05
Analysis	0.801 ^(**)	0.000	D at 0.05
Contact	0.821 ^(**)	0.000	Slab 0.01
Structure and operations	0.862 ^(**)	0.002	Slab 0.01
Culture and awareness organizers	0.854 ^(**)	0.003	D at 0.05
** D at 0.01			
* D at 0.05 indicative level			

Table 3 shows that all the paragraphs of each axis are statistically significantly correlated with the overall score, as the values of the coefficient of correlation are strong between the axes and the total score, which is higher than the statistically accepted value (0.70), and therefore all paragraphs have a degree of internal consistency.

Stability test: The stability test means that the questionnaire gives the same result if it is redistributed more than once under the same conditions and conditions and that the stability test is under the equation (Cronbach Alfe) Cron-NebaX Alpha, in the case of the test in which the grades are at a rate (not one and zero), but can take different values (1, 2, 3, 4.) As in the case of tests that use the Leckert ladder, this equation is also used in objective or pests.

Table (3) Test the stability of search variables using the Cron-Nebach Alpha coefficient

T	Variables	Crewe Nebach Alpha Laboratory
1	Viral Marketing	0.957
2	Competitive intelligence	0.912
3	Total	0.920

It is clear from the results shown in the table above that the value of the Kronbach Alpha coefficient is high for each of the research variables, and the total value of the research variables for alpha coefficients (0.920), which is a high stability value, this result confirms the sincerity and stability of the study questionnaire and its validity to apply to the sample of the basic study, analysis of results and answer to the study questions and testing their hypotheses.

The statistical tools and methods used in data processing and analysis:

The researcher relied on several statistical tools and methods, as follows:

Spss-Ver-23 package: used to extract results.

Microsoft Excel 2010 for data analysis.

Study results

The results of question 1: What is the impact of viral marketing on the competitive intelligence of Iraqi fashion house managers?

To answer the main question of the study, the researcher calculated the arithmetic averages and percentages of performance on the same scale, and the results were as follows:

Table (4) Results of answering the study question

Phrase No.	Phrase	Average arithmetic	Percentage
1	I follow some of the electronic ads that appear to me while browsing websites.	3,2	45%
2	find that viral campaigns are a new and unconventional way of promoting the product electronically.	2,1	76%

3	The viral campaign content drives me to want to search more about the product.	2,4	45%
4	The diversity of the content of the message using images or videos is more attractive to the attention of the users of the networking sites.	4,3	65%
5	The content of the viral message is easy to spread, which leads many to communicate easily through networking sites.	2.1	55%
6	Viral campaigns with satirical content are more accepted and widespread among users.	3,6	67%
7	Viral campaigns with pessimistic content are more accepted and widespread among users.	2,9	87%
8	Exposure to viral campaigns with unusually strange content is more acceptable and widespread among users.	4,3	65%
9	The content of the viral campaign with innovative ideas is fast spreading among the users.	3,1	77%
10	The clear viral campaign content contributes to a mental image of the product.	2.6	65%
11	Social media has a prominent role in publishing and following advertising campaigns about a product.	1.2	76%
12	An E-mail has a prominent role in publishing and following advertising campaigns about a product.	2,5	86%
13	The company's website has a prominent role in publishing and following advertising campaigns about a product.	3.4	65%
14	Promotional gifts are an incentive for customers to interact with marketing campaigns	4.5	66%
15	I have already received a financial incentive to resend a message I received from a company to others.	4.2	76%
16	I purchase a product after hearing a recommendation from a relative or friend.	4.3	87%
17	Listen to the opinions and experiences of others about a pre-purchase product.	2.4	88%
18	My working group transmits the advertising messages you receive among themselves to stimulate your purchase.	4.3	76%
19	Exposure to viral messages helps me make the purchase decision.	3.4	56%
20	Viral messages help me to announce my point of view of a product.	3.3	66%
21	I find viral messages attractive and push me to make a purchase decision.	4.2	78%
22	Internet advertising raises the need for products I have never used before so I make purchases.	3.4	73%
23	The arrival of viral messages from friends contributes to increased persuasion and purchase	3.4	65%
24	Photos and videos in any viral ad help me make the purchase decision.	4.3	82%
25	The organization prepares plans for competitive intelligence.	4.5	84%
26	The organization's management is very interested in the strategies of its competitors.	4.2	73%
27	The organization's management constantly monitors the technology used by competing organizations in the light of their plans.	3.2	88%
28	The organization's management is concerned with monitoring and evaluating the activities and plans of competing organizations.	1.2	54%
29	The organization's management holds regular meetings with employees to clarify competitive intelligence plans.	2.2	38%
30	The organization prepares plans for competitive intelligence.	3.2	65%
31	The organization's management has several ways to provide the requirements of competitive intelligence plans.	3,6	67%
32	Employees return to the information base via computers to discover marketing opportunities.	2,9	87%
33	The organization relies on efficient staff in the marketing intelligence system to collect and analyze data and information about competitors.	4,3	65%
34	The organization is keen to keep up to date with its data and information on the movements of competitors.	3,1	77%
35	The organization collects information on the management style adopted by competing organizations.	2.6	65%

36	THE ORGANIZATION REGULARLY FORMULATES RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT PLANS AND ANALYSES THEM AND NEW PRODUCTS FOR COMPETITORS.	1,2	76%
37	The organization relies on an analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats to determine a competitive situation.	2,5	86%
38	The organization analyzes the strategies and trends of future competitors.	3,4	65%
39	The organization follows up on information posted online to analyze the competitor's R&D programs.	2,4	45%
40	The organization analyzes information that can give the organization a competitive advantage.	4,3	65%
41	The organization provides information on competitive intelligence to all employees of the organization.	2,1	55%
42	The organization seeks to develop effective communication systems to win potential customers.	3,6	67%
43	The organization is keen to improve communication technology as the key to achieving superiority over competitors.	2,9	87%
44	The organization relies on a flexible organizational structure that is consistent with contemporary developments in competitive intelligence.	2,4	45%
45	The organization provides the requirements for competitive intelligence processes for employees.	4,3	65%
46	The organization uses techniques to help with customer-related processes.	2,5	86%
47	The organization adopts teams Efficient For research and development to improve its product portfolio and operations.	3,4	65%
48	The organization is one of the core values of its culture.	2,4	45%
49	The organization's organizational culture is based on looking at employees like customers and making their satisfaction a priority.	4,3	65%
50	The organization's culture encourages creativity based on competitive intelligence.	2,5	86%
51	The organization's culture encourages teamwork and collaboration among those working in the field of competitive intelligence.	3,4	65%

The results show that 45 percent of the population is in the country. Of the sample members of the study, 76% were able to carry out viral campaigns. Of the sample members of the study have electronic publishing methods, and spends (45%) Of the study sample members in physical stimulation, preferably (65%) Of the study's respondents, influential opinion leaders (55%) Sample members prefer the decision to buy, preferably (67%) Of the sample members of the study, planning, and concentration, and in the collection and analysis of information, 87% of the population from the study sample members. The following table shows the views of the study sample members with all the answers to the questionnaire:

Table (5) Opinions of study sample members

Strongly agree.	Agreed	Neutral	I don't agree.	I don't agree strongly.
65%	23%	2%	4%	4%

It is clear from the table and figure above that the response rate to the alternative (strongly agreed) was (65 percent). It is the highest percentage of alternatives to the answer, which means that there is an impact in the paragraphs of the variable viral marketing on the paragraphs of competitive intelligence and the researcher explained this result to the nature of the administrative experience enjoyed by the managers of the Iraqi fashion house in addition to having competitive experience in highlighting their creative work in their job.

Test hypotheses of the study

In this study, the hypotheses of the study developed in the study methodology, which relate to variables, will be tested.

The study, which is represented by viral marketing as an independent variable, and the dependent variable of competitive intelligence.

1- Testing the **hypothesis of correlation:** This research seeks to determine the nature of the relationship between the variables of the study, to determine the extent to which the first main hypothesis is accepted or rejected: there is a statistical correlation with positive moral significance for the marketing of the virus with competitive intelligence, using the simple correlation coefficient (Pearson Correlation Coefficient), which is one of the statistical methods used to measure the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables at the level of the sample studied.

It is clear from Table 6, figure 2, to a positive correlation with positive moral significance (expulsion), between viral marketing, competitive intelligence, at the macro level, and the correlation relationship was valued at (0.751**), at the level of indication (0.01), and the number of moral relationships (5) is the highest sub-value of the correlation transactions in this axis between viral marketing, Competitive intelligence, valued at 0.863**, at a level of significance (0.01), reflects the existence of a relationship of moral significance and explains the strength of the relationship, hence the acceptance of the first main hypothesis that there is a statistical correlation of positive moral significance to competitive intelligence.

(**) A link of moral significance at the level of (0.01).

(*) A link of moral significance at the level of (0.05).

Figure 2) The link between viral marketing and competitive intelligence

Table No. 6 : Correlation between Viral Marketing and Competitive Intelligence**2. Testing of impact hypotheses**

The current study developed the second and third main hypothesis, which is the simple effect hypothesis.

Simple Regression Analysis)(Multi Regression Analysis) ‘

1- Simple Regression Analysis

It is clear from Table 7 and Figures 3 that the calculated (F) values (28.21), which is greater than the (F)scheduled value(6.90) at the level of indication (0.01), morally (0.000), and a degree of freedom (1.90), and this result means the effect of the transponder (**viral marketing**) in the variable (**competitive intelligence**).

The value of the R^2 , a descriptive measure used to explain the usefulness of the slope equation in the estimation of values, and represent the ratio of error reduction when using the regression equation, was 0.744, which means that (**viral marketing**) explains the ratio (74.4%)of the variation in (**competitive intelligence**), and that(25.6%)is an unexplained variation of factors that did not enter the slope. These findings, therefore, provide sufficient support to accept the second major research effect hypothesis, which states that "**there is a morally significant effect of viral marketingin competitive intelligence**".

Through table(7)we note that the value of the fixed limit (a=0.651) is statistically moral, as the value of t calculated for it(3.532)which is greater than the t table at the level of moral 1% and the degree of freedom(90)and the amount(2.35), and the value of the slope Haddi(b=1.131)is statistically moral because the calculated t value of 15.589) is greater than the tabloid t at the moral level of 1% and the degree of freedom(90) and the amount of (2.35), these results confirm the presence of a strong effect of viral **marketing** in government spending.

Table 7 shows the impact of viral marketing with competitive intelligence

Child variable Independent variable		Competitive intelligence							
		Fixed limit A	Value t Calculated	The slope of the slope B	Value t Calculated	The number of people who have been identified in the first ^{year} of	Calculated F value	Moral	Resolution
Viral Marketing X Competitive intelligence And	Link coefficient	.863**	.813**	.670**	.651**	.751**	5	100%	
	Moral level	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
	Resolution	Daleh	Daleh	Daleh	Daleh	Daleh			
		0.651	3.532	1.131	15.589	0.744	28.21	0.000	There's an effect.

* The value of (F)table at a moral level of 0.05- and 2-degreesfreedom (1.90) = (3.92)

** The (F)tab amount value at a moral level of 0.01 and 2 degrees of freedom (1.90) =(6.90)

* The value of (T)table at a moral level of 0.05- and 2-degreesfreedom (90) = (1.66)

** T tab amount value at a moral level of 0.01- and 2-degreesfreedom (90) =(2.35)

Fig. 3 demonstrates the impact of viral marketing with competitive intelligence

2- (Multi Regression Analysis)

The study methodology put the third main hypothesis that the dimensions of viral marketing (electronic publishing means, physical stimulation, influential opinion leaders, purchasing decision) combined morally and positively in competitive intelligence. This result means a statistically moral effect of the transponder (total variables (X) in the variable (competitive intelligence), in the research sample. 2 %) Of the variation in (competitive intelligence), and (17.8%) It is an explained variation of factors that did not enter the regression model. These results, therefore, provide sufficient support for the acceptance of the third major multi-research hypothesis, which states that there is an amorally significant effect of the total variables(X) viral marketing in competitive intelligence.

Through table8, we note that the value of the fixed limit ($a=0.820$) is statistically moral, as the value of t calculated for it(3.077) which is greater than t table at the moral level of 1% and the degree of freedom (87) and the degree of freedom (2.35), while the value of the marginal slope of (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4), amounted to ($b=0.1$), and amounted to ($b=0.1$). 19, 0.344, 0.012, 0.693) respectively are statistically moral because the value of t calculated for them(6.274, 5.181, 4.211, 1.711)is greater than the t -scale (2.35) at the level of indication (0.01) and freely (87).

In light of these results, it is clear that viral marketing with its combined variables has a strong moral impact on the competitive intelligence of Iraqi fashion house managers.

Table No. (8)TheMulti-VariableEffect(X) Viral Marketingin Respiratory Intelligence

Viral Marketing	Competitive intelligence						
	Regression coefficients	t Calculated	Moral	Selection coefficient R ²	F Calculated	Moral	Resolution
Fixed limit	0.820	3.077	0.003	0.822	12.83	0.000	There's an effect.
Electronic publishing	0.119	6.274	0.000				
Physical stimulation	0.344	5.181	0.000				
Influential opinion leaders	0.012	4.217	0.005				
Purchase decision	0.693	1.711	0.009				

* The value of (F)table at a moral level of 0.05 and 2 degrees of freedom (4.87) = (2.46)

** The value of (F)table at a moral level of 0.01 and 2 degrees of freedom (4.87) =(3.52)

* The value of (T)table at a moral level of 0.05 and 2 degrees freedom (87)=(1.66)

** T tab amount value at a moral level of 0.01 and 2 degrees of freedom (87) =(2.35)

Conclusions:

1. The current research sample members are provided with the ability to market viral in their work.

2. The members of the current research sample are characterized by competitive intelligence in their work which makes them more creative in providing what they have.
3. There is a positive correlation between viral marketing and competitive intelligence in the current research sample.

Proposals:

In light of the current research results, the researcher suggests:

1. The need to use the tools and results of the current research in conducting an extensive study targeting government economic institutions that contribute through the research variables to the strengthening of the Iraqi economy.
2. Work on the preparation of development training programs based on viral marketing models and competitive training for department staff.
3. Work on a descriptive survey aimed at diagnosing viral marketing and competitive intelligence among Iraqi oil company managers.

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